

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PRESEPSIN AS A MARKER FOR RISK STRATIFICATION FOR ACUTE CHOLANGITIS IN SURGERY DEPARTMENT

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Abstract

Acute cholangitis is caused by bacterial infection and has high morbidity and mortality risk. The grade of cholangitis can guide clinical treatment from single antibiotic treatment to biliary drainage. With the introduction of C-reactive protein (CRP), and total bilirubin (T-Bil), procalcitonin into the diagnostic criteria and severity grading for acute cholangitis, the diagnosis rate and grading have significantly improved.

Aim. To evaluate the value of presepsin in patients with acute cholangitis.

Methods. Overall, this study enrolled all patients (age > 18 years) diagnosed with acute cholangitis from January 2018 till December 2022. All patients included in this study met the diagnostic criteria for acute cholangitis according to TG18.

Results. In total, 249 patients were examined, which included 70, 80, and 99 patients classified as having mild, moderate, and severe cholangitis, respectively. WBC count, CRP, PCT, presepsin, T-Bil, direct bilirubin, and sequential organ failure assessment scores of moderate and severe cholangitis patients were higher than those of mild cholangitis patients ($P = <0.001$). The optimal cutoff value of presepsin for grading moderate acute cholangitis was 1490 pg/mL (sensitivity, 0.84; specificity, 0.56) The optimal cutoff value of presepsin for grading severe acute cholangitis was 2635 pg/mL (sensitivity, 0.64; specificity, 0.78).

Conclusion. Presepsin can help predict the positive blood culture, and is also superior to CRP and PCT in the risk stratification of acute cholangitis. Timely determination of presepsin levels can help clinicians identify the severity of patients with acute cholangitis early.

Keywords: Acute cholangitis, procalcitonin, presepsin, diagnostic.

Introduction. Acute cholangitis is a systemic infectious disease characterized by biliary obstruction and bile bacterial growth that cause acute inflammation and infection of the bile duct. Acute cholangitis was first described by Charcot as ‘hepatic fever’ in 1877; therefore, the typical signs and symptoms of acute cholangitis (intermittent fever with chills, right-upper-quadrant pain and jaundice) are known as Charcot’s triad [1,2].

The prevalence of cholelithiasis varies from race to race. Of the many patients hospitalized for gallstones, 6% to 9% are diagnosed with acute cholangitis [3]. Men and women are affected equally and the average age of patients with acute cholangitis is between 50 and 60 years old. If acute cholangitis is not properly treated, it rapidly develops into systemic inflammatory response syndrome, sepsis and mortality. In the 1990s, the mortality rate for severe acute cholangitis was between 11% and 27% [4].

Presepsin (sCD14-subtype [sCD14-ST]) was discovered in 2002 by Endo et al. [4] When monocytes and granulocytes phagocytose bacteria, CD14 is taken up into the cell together with the bacteria. CD14 that is digested and cleaved by intracellular digestive enzymes is otherwise named presepsin [5,6]. Increased presepsin is considered specific for bacterial infections and useful for early diagnosis of bacterial infections [7]. Presepsin can be used as a biomarker in the emergency room and intensive care unit (ICU) settings since only 17 min are required for its measurement [8].

Therefore, this prospective study aimed to compare levels of presepsin against traditional biomarkers in patients with acute cholangitis on admission to evaluate the role of presepsin in the early risk stratification of acute cholangitis.

Material and methods: Overall, this study enrolled all patients (age > 18 years) diagnosed with acute cholangitis from January 2018 till December 2022.

All patients included in this study met the diagnostic criteria for acute cholangitis according to TG18. The diagnostic criteria were as follows: (1) Systemic inflammation (fever/chills, abnormal WBC count, or elevated CRP level); (2) cholestasis (T-Bil levels ≥ 34.2 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$ or liver enzyme levels > 1.5 times that of the normal upper limit); and (3) supporting imaging findings (evidence of biliary dilatation, such as benign or malignant stenosis, stone, and/or stent). The severity was stratified as mild, moderate, and severe according to TG18[12].

A chemiluminescent enzyme immunoassay was used to test presepsin concentration by a PATHFAST analyzer (Mitsubishi Chemical Medience Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). The detection range was 20 pg/mL to 200000 pg/mL. Information regarding conventional inflammatory biomarkers procalcitonin, C-reactive protein and other indicators were obtained from the clinical laboratory data.

Results: The surveyed patients with acute cholangitis who took part in this study were 249. All patients with acute cholangitis at admission were divided into

mild, moderate and severe groups based on the TG18 score. The number of patients in the above three groups was 70 (28.1%), 80 (32.1%) and 99 (39.8%), respectively.

The features and outcomes of 249 patients with acute cholangitis are shown in Table 1. There were 156

men and 93 women, and the median age was 71 years. Age, WBC counts, CRP, PCT, presepsin, T-Bilirubin and direct bilirubin, of moderate and severe cholangitis patients were higher than those of mild cholangitis patients.

Table 1

Features	Severity of acute cholangitis			p-value
	Mild (n=70)	Moderate (n=80)	Severe (n=99)	
Age	67	83	75	0.000
Male/Female	55/15	57/23	44/55	0.780
Temperature (°C)	38.1 (37.7-38.4)	38.7 (38.1-39.2)	38.9 (38.4-39.4)	0.017
<i>Laboratory tests</i>				
WBCs ($\times 10^9/L$)	8.90 (6.35-10.95)	14.25 (9.98-17.05)	10.95 (7.75-16.35)	<0.001
CRP (mg/L)	52.29 (25.87-115.50)	88.95 (57.90-150.58)	120.65 (66.75-180.58)	<0.001
PCT (ng/mL)	4.28 (1.03-11.28)	10.34 (1.64-31.75)	25.55 (5.75-48.56)	<0.001
Presepsin (pg/mL)	1429.00 (825.00-1875.00)	2225.00 (1689.00-2704.00)	3215.00 (2185.00-3915.00)	<0.001
T-Bil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	62.58 (45.30-103.58)	113.4 (85.45-157.45)	99.98 (59.78-150.02)	<0.001
D-Bil ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	40.55 (29.55-76.82)	77.50 (59.45-99.54)	69.77 (42.37-97.34)	<0.001

After comparing the three groups, WBC counts, CRP, PCT, presepsin and T-Bilirubin of patients with moderate and severe cholangitis were found to be higher than those of patients with mild cholangitis ($P < 0.001$; Table 1). Multiple comparison analysis was used to check the differences between particular pairs of groups. Presepsin had the lowest P-value in patients with mild-to-moderate and moderate-to-severe acute cholangitis ($P < 0.001$). The optimal cutoff value of presepsin for grading moderate acute cholangitis was

1490 pg/mL (sensitivity, 0.84; specificity, 0.56). The optimal cutoff value of presepsin for grading severe acute cholangitis was 2635 pg/mL (sensitivity, 0.64; specificity, 0.78).

Compared with the mild group, presepsin, procalcitonin, and CRP levels were significantly higher in patients with moderate and severe acute cholangitis ($P < 0.001$). Dependence of number of microorganisms and grades of acute cholangitis Table 2.

Table 2

Features	Severity of acute cholangitis			p-value
	Mild (n=70)	Moderate (n=80)	Severe (n=99)	
Blood culture	65 ()	72	89	0.315
Positive blood culture	19	29	38	0.147
G ⁻ bacteria	15	22	32	0.328
G ⁺ bacteria	0	2	5	
Other bacteria	2	3	3	0.548

WBC counts, PCT, and presepsin levels in the positive blood culture group were greater than those in the negative blood culture group ($P < 0.01$); however, CRP and T-Bil levels did not show significant differences between the groups ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion: For a long time, acute cholangitis has been diagnosed based on Charcot's triad; however, its misdiagnosis rate can be as high as 30%–80% [1]. With the introduction of WBC count, CRP, and T-Bilirubin the diagnosis rate and grading have improved notably [9,10]. However, early risk stratification assessments are difficult according to WBC count, CRP, T-Bilirubin, vital signs in the surgery department. PCT has been recommended as a biomarker for predicting severe acute cholangitis; however, PCT levels are often higher in patients with burns [11], and are falsely negative in patients with atypical bacterial infections [12]. Early grading of acute cholangitis is still an important clinical challenge in the surgery department. Presepsin is a promising biomarker of bacterial infectious disease

discovered in recent years, and its sensitivity and accuracy are better than those of PCT, WBC count, and CRP [13,14]. Based on the aforementioned findings, we demonstrated that presepsin had a higher sensitivity and specificity in risk stratification of acute cholangitis and had a better positive rate in predicting bacterial blood culture.

Blood cultures are the gold standard for diagnosing bloodstream infections, especially when a serious infection is suspected; however, blood cultures are often negative, and the results usually arrive after several days [15,16]. In this study, presepsin was as effective as PCT in predicting positive bacterial cultures. Presepsin levels can be determined much sooner than blood culture, facilitating early risk stratification and treatment to some extent.

Conclusion: Presepsin can help predict the positive blood culture, and is also superior to CRP and PCT

in the risk stratification of acute cholangitis. Timely determination of presepsin levels can help clinicians identify the severity of patients with acute cholangitis early.

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